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Discopexy associated with eminectomy for the treatment of recurrent TMJ dislocation

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Summary

Introduction: Temporomandibular joint dislocation occurs when the head of the mandible moves out of the joint fossa, causing the posterior surface of the head of the mandible to be in front of the articular tubercle. When episodes occur and frequent, this condition is referred to as recurrent dislocation. Although there are different treatments, discopexy associated with eminectomy is a surgical option with satisfactory results and favorable prognosis. **Case report:** This paper reports the case of a patient with severe recurrent dislocations, limitation of mouth opening, frequent

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headaches and pain when eating, surgically treated by discopexy associated with eminectomy. The patient has a stable 24-month follow-up, without symptoms or new episodes of dislocation. The multidisciplinary approach has a high success rate, and surgical procedures should be considered when clinical procedures such as physiotherapy, thermotherapy and occlusal devices fail. **Final considerations:** Discopexy associated with eminectomy shows good results in the treatment of recurrent TMJ dislocation, with minimal chances of recurrence or joint damage. After surgery, patients show good joint function.

Key Words: Luxação , Disfunção temporomandibular. Cirurgia da articulação temporomandibular.

INTRODUCTION

The temporomandibular joint (TMJ) is certainly one of the most complex joints in the body. It is basically composed of hard parts and soft parts, considering the bone joint surfaces as hard parts and the joint cartilage, joint disc, synovial membrane, joint capsule and TMJ ligaments as soft parts.

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The TMJ can be affected by several disorders called temporomandibular disorders (TMD), which, in addition to involving the TMJ, may also be related to the masticatory muscles or to both concomitantly. Among the causes of disorders directly related to the TMJ, the main ones are loss of medial, lateral or anterior support of the joint disc, in addition to loss of posterior support of the disc or joint wear.

Diagnosis and treatment should always be focused on an evidence-based approach. Clinical and imaging examinations are extremely important to be able to identify the cause of orofacial pain and define the conduct, in which tomography, arthrography and, especially, magnetic resonance imaging may be used.

Firstly, a conservative treatment should be implemented, preferably minimally invasive and reversible, for a period of approximately three months. re-establishment of adequate sleep, which enables correct muscle and joint repair.

If the result is unfavorable, the diagnosis should be reviewed, and consultation with another professional colleague in the health area is also indicated, regarding other possible comorbidities and, if it is perceived that there is no other conservative treatment method that can be implemented, the surgical approach may be indicated.

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Surgical treatment includes minimally invasive techniques, such as arthrocentesis or arthroscopy, and invasive techniques, such as discectomy, discectomy in cases of articular disc damage, arthroplasty or total reconstruction of the TMJ with alloplastic material in cases of joint degeneration. The oral and maxillofacial surgeon must correctly indicate the surgical modality that will bring the best cost-benefit to his patient.

This article aims to describe a case in which discectomy associated with eminectomy was performed as a surgical alternative in a patient who had unsuccessful conservative treatments to relieve facial pain, discussing the characteristics of joint disorders and the forms of treatment.

CASE REPORT

Female patient, 42 years old, Caucasian, attended the Oral and Maxillofacial Surgery and Traumatology Service at Hospital São Camilo Ipiranga (SP), reporting chronic pain in the bilateral TMJ region with approximately 8 years of duration, which had significantly increased in the 6 months prior to the initial demand for assistance. He also reported having difficulty opening his mouth, which was found to be approximately 22 mm and limited opening.

anterior displacement of articular discs without reduction/recapture, degenerative changes and joint effusion.

Figure 1 – Closed-mouth magnetic resonance imaging where we can observe the displacement of the articular disc.

Figure 2 – Magnetic resonance imaging with the mouth open, where we can observe the displacement of the articular disc without recapture.

The proposed initial treatment comprised the clinical approach in which non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs, muscle relaxants were used to control pain, use of occlusal devices, thermotherapy and physiotherapy. although the patient's complaints were not eliminated. It was decided, then, to perform surgical treatment, choosing the surgical procedure of bilateral discopexy, with disc anchorage through open surgery associated with eminectomy.

Figure 3- Occlusal Device (Michigan Plate)

The endaural surgical access was chosen (Figure 4A) for the temporomandibular joint and exposure of the joint disc, condyle and glenoid cavity. After access, the components of the joint were analyzed in detail, adhesions were removed and the disc was manually repositioned. Excessive tissue in the bilaminar region of the disc was removed, sutured, and the entire structure was fixed with a non-resorbable Mitek-type anchor in the posterior region of

the condyle (Figure 4B. After fixing the articular disc, mandibular movements were tested to verify of stability.

Figure 4 A– Endaural Access. Figure 4B- Fixed anchor and stable disc structure.

Figure 5 A– Endaural suture. Figure 5 B- Eminectomy

Figure 6 – Immediate postoperative image (Rx) where we can observe the excellent positioning of the anchors.

After 7 days of postoperative, the patient remained in the physiotherapy treatment, performing 30 functional sessions and evolved without pain complaints, reporting an improvement in her quality of life. At the moment, she has a mouth opening of 40.3 mm (Figure 3A), having been followed up for a period of 2 years, demonstrating stability in her mandibular movements and satisfaction with the treatment (Figure 7).

Figure 7 – Patient with a maximum mouth opening of 40.3 mm after the last physiotherapy session.

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DISCUSSION

The main clinical findings of a normal TMJ include a maximum opening in the range of 40 mm or more (when presented below 20 mm, there may be a possible intracapsular problem), absence of pain, absence of restriction in movements and absence of noise and crackles.

TMD includes any disharmony of the temporomandibular joints, the muscles of the stomatognathic apparatus and the vascular and nervous supplies of these tissues, characterized by pain, joint noises and facial deformities and limitation of mandibular movements.

The evaluation of the patient who presents with pain, temporomandibular disorder, or both, is analogous to any other method of diagnostic investigation. It should include a complete medical history, thorough clinical examination, functional examination of the masticatory system, and some type of routine radiographic examination of the TMJ, such as panoramic face radiography, conventional TMJ tomography, TMJ computed tomography, nuclear magnetic resonance, and arthrography. from ATM.

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The literature is quite variable in terms of etiology⁶ and available treatments for TMJ disorders, but the consensus is based on the fact that conservative treatment must be addressed prior to existing surgical procedures.⁷ Many patients can be successfully treated, for through non-surgical methods such as physiotherapy, moist heat, occlusal splint, pharmacotherapy, arthrocentesis or intra-articular injections. However, about 5% of patients in whom conservative therapy fails require open TMJ surgery.⁸ These same authors state that the role of open TMJ surgery for the treatment of pain and temporomandibular disorders gained new prominence when they were recognized the importance of disc displacement and deformity as the primary cause of TMJ pain and dysfunction.

The indication for TMJ surgical procedures is related to functional and morphological changes, tumor processes and degenerative changes, with the aim of improving pain, quality of life and restoring function. Surgical procedures available for treating disc and adnexa displacement are assisted mandibular manipulation with increased hydrostatic pressure, arthrocentesis, arthroscopy, and arthrotomy. Arthrotomy can be subdivided into disc anchorage (discopexy), tuberculotomy, disc repositioning, discectomy with or without interposition of material, condylectomy with graft or total joint replacement. failure in the conservative treatment and also because

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it deals with the repositioning of the joint disc which, in the case of the patient, was displaced from its anatomical position. Performing the surgery must be associated with clinical treatment, in which a specialized physiotherapist and oral and maxillofacial surgeon will identify areas of tension generation throughout the body to optimize the surgical result and thus prevent a new degenerative cycle .

In this context, oral and maxillofacial surgeons should keep in mind that the surgical approach should not be considered the first choice when facial pain is reported. However, under conditions of persistent and chronic symptoms, alternatives such as discopexy and temporomandibular joint surgery may be considered to improve the patient's quality of life.

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

Therapeutic success is based on making a correct diagnosis, on the professional's experience and on the surgical techniques used. Both surgical and non-surgical approaches can be used in the treatment of TMD, depending on the etiology and severity of the disease. Treatment aims to relieve symptoms and, consequently, improve the quality of life of patients. Less invasive treatments should be used primarily and, in cases of failure, more invasive

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treatments should be considered, although open surgery should be used when the joint presents disc displacement and there is no remission of signs and symptoms by conservative therapies .

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